

Mathematical Analysis of The Sustainable City with Concept of Buffering of Pollution

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Abstract

In this report, making a game with the graph of the sustainable city with buffering of pollution, and suggested some theoretical conjectures with the characteristics of that game.

1 Introduction

Living in the earth inevitably involves living together with nature. Without nature, people can't live in the earth, and without nature, people lost mean of existing themselves. but by indiscreet development, greed for resources and technology of human, the earth is devastating. And this devastating works fatal to us. To solve this problem, the international community has continued to emphasize encouraging citizens and their governments to encourage 'living with nature', and this effort has led to various new concepts, including sustainable city.

In this report, explaining the necessary condition and conjectures about methods to form sustainable city.

2 Materials and Methods

The theoretical background is a graph of discrete mathematical meanings. The graph is a mathematical object represented by $G = (V, E)$, where V and E are sets of vertices and sides, respectively.

Key words and phrases: Sustainable City, Graph, Game

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Figure 1: Path

Briefly explaining, let define Vertex set and Edge set as following, $V = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$, $E = \{\{0, 1\}, \{1, 2\}, \{2, 3\}\}$, The graph (V, E) can be expressed as figure 1.

Figure 2: Petersen Graph

Figure 2 is representative example of graph, vertexes appear like points, and edges appear as lines. It is obvious that the number of elements of the set of vertexes is 10, and the number of elements of the set is 15.

Figure 3: K_5

Complete graph is a graph in which all vertices are connected by edges as shown in figure 3. There is a big difference in meaning from the perfect graph, so be careful to use the term. When the vertex is n , write this graph as K_n .

Figure 4: Star Graph

Star graph is a graph that has all the other vertexes connected to one vertex and does not contain any other connections as shown in figure 4.

Finally, the bipartite graph is a graph in which the vertexes are divided into two sets and the vertexes of the same set are not connected to each other as shown in figure 5. And the complete bipartite graph is that the vertexes belonging to different sets are all connected to each other as shown in figure 6,

When the numbers of elements of a finite set of finite points are respectively m, n , the graph is denoted $K_{m,n}$. [1]

3 Results

Using the above theoretical background, Producing various results was able to by developing mathematical logic. Representative results, including definitions of games relating to the layout of sustainable cities, and related theorems, are briefly described here.

3.1 Definition of A Game related to The Arrangement of The Structures of the Sustainable City

Assuming that the composition of a city is made up only of a combination of 'town' and 'park', and given the design of such an sustainable city, a graph can be constructed with the following definition.

Definition 1. *All structures are represented by vertices, and adjacent structures are connected by edges. (The structure means town and park.)*

If the graph derived from the above definition is $G = (V, E)$, the graph shows the arrangement of the sustainable city structure abstractly but absolutely well. Now the following definition is the small-definition to distinguish between town and park in the graph without the design.

Definition 2. *G has weights of 1 for the vertexes that represent the city, and a weight of 0 for the parks.*

Now that all of the graphs have configured, so our game can be design with the following definition. The purpose of this game is to evaluate the efficiency of the arrangement of the structures inside the sustainable city. Therefore, the number of parks and towns between the graphs participating in the game should be equal. Otherwise, an ecological city with a structure that has a much larger number of parks than the number of town centers will have an big advantage, unconditionally.

Definition 3. *1. The element of the game is the time and pollution index.
2. At every time, the town makes 1 pollution and sends arithmetical average of*

- 1 to adjacent park.
- 3. At every time, the park removes 0.5 pollution.
- 4. At every time, the park communicates pollution to the park adjacent to itself on arithmetical average.

The fourth proposition of the definition above is the concept of pollution buffer. The pollution is buffered by being dispersed.

The objects participating in the game are abstraction of the structure of the sustainable city with the same number of parks and town, and the graph that is judged to be the most dominant in the game is the graph with the most uniform distribution of pollution on the average. The reason for this definition is that, in the third definition of the game, parks are written as that remove 0.5 pollution every time, but this value is not certain. However, it can be believed that the rate of removing pollution is faster when the case where the pollutants are spread as much as possible.

In the example, judging by common sense, Example 1 that the more dominant graph in Example 1 and 2 is shown in the following figure.

Inductively applying the above inference, then, it is evident that the top dominant graph in the game is complete bipartite graph of the park and the town. However, there is a considerable error in this reasoning: this sustainable city must be on a flat surface. It is easy to think that all graphs can be projected in a plane. In following Kuratowski's theorem [3], the necessary and sufficient conditions for a plane graph was shown.

Theorem 1. *A finite graph is planar if and only if it does not contain a subgraph that is a subdivision of K_5 (the complete graph on five vertices) or of $K_{3,3}$.*

As a result of this theorem, if the elements of the ecological city are formed as shown in figure 6, the park and the city center can not be adjacent to each other. Therefore, the following two conjectures, which deregulate the above strong proposition, are introduced without proof.

Conjecture 2. *The sustainable city is constituted inductively in the aspects of the town.*

Explaining this conjecture with examples, Suppose that an sustainable city is top dominant, as in Example 3. So, where sustainable city will be created by adding the town here? The answer is Example 4. At this time, the shape of Example 3 is not damaged at all. In other words, adding a town does not destroy the existing layout. The true meaning of this conjecture is that when the number of parks is constant, the connections of the first sustainable city

graph will be preserved no matter how much the town is added in the graph. This is combined with the following conjecture.

Conjecture 3. *The most stable arrangement of the sustainable city structure is made by combining the town as much as possible with the park with the least degree in the previous arrangement (the arrangement of fewer cities).*

The degree of a vertex means the number of edges connected to the vertex. This conjecture is to determine which park is connected to new town as in Example 3, 4 above. The correct answer is that it connects to both ends of the park, as shown in Example 4. This is because the central park is already receiving pollutants from four existing towns. Thus, the new town must be connected to the parks at both ends to maximize the distribution of pollutants. Conjecture 3 is the extension of this.

4 Discussion

Two conjectures about sustainable city as above have introduced as above, but there are no sufficient logical proofs here. There was an attempt to prove it, but it was frustrated because it was abstruse. The conjecture above would be even more valuable if the proofs are supported. The proofs of these will be shown in a subsequent study.

5 Conclusion

Conjecture. *The sustainable city is constituted inductively in the aspects of the town.*

Conjecture. *The most stable arrangement of the sustainable city structure is made by combining the town as much as possible with the park with the least degree in the previous arrangement (the arrangement of fewer cities).*

The above two theorems are presented, which seems to construct sustainable cities more efficient.

6 References

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